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ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANTS IN CULINARY HERBS AND SPICES - WHAT GOES AROUND COMES AROUND

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Environmental pollutants are substances that pollute the natural environment, causing adverse effects on ecosystems as well as human health. The most common types of such pollutants, originating both from the environment and from anthropogenic activities, are polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and toxic metals. As many as 16 of the many compounds that structurally belong to the PAHs group, including the most famous benzo(a)pyrene, have been classified as human carcinogens. Regarding toxic metals, cadmium and arsenic are also proven carcinogens, while lead is classified as probable. This study presents an overview of the contamination of culinary herbs and spices with PAHs and toxic metals, based on thirteen years (2011-2023) of data recorded in the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF). RASFF is an EU-based system established to coordinate responses and action taken in order to protect public health. The company's own check (47.9%) and official control on the market (40.8%) were the mechanisms by which the majority of 71 violations were detected, of which 43 were related to the presence of PAHs and 24 to toxic metals. PAHs were found mostly in ginger, paprika and bay leaf. Among the toxic metals, lead was recorded the most, with 16 notifications (of which one third related to turmeric), followed by cadmium (6), mercury (4) and arsenic (1). As a whole, products such as paprika (11.3%), pepper (8.4%), bay leaf (7.0%) and many others, with raw materials mostly originating from China (18.3%), but also from India, Vietnam and other countries, stood out as being of public health concern, in most cases (85.9%) serious, causing about two-thirds of notifications to be classified as warnings (67.6%). The severity of the toxic effects caused by environmental pollutants, including carcinogenicity, strongly argues for risk management actions aimed at ensuring food safety and thereby protecting public health.

Keywords: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, Toxic metals, Food safety, Public health